

Dezincification of Brasses

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Dezincification is the term applied to the preferential corrosion of zinc from copper-zinc alloys. It may be easily recognised by the copper-coloured appearance of the corroded metal. The selective corrosion of the base metal from the alloy is encountered in many cases, e.g., aluminium from aluminium bronzes or tin from tin bronzes. Dezincification of brass is the best example of the selective corrosion and it has been studied extensively for many years. There is, however, still disagreement about the mechanism of dezincification. The theories centre round the two main views. According to one view copper produced is residual, whereas the other view encompasses that copper is of the redeposited type. In the former, it is supposed that zinc is preferentially dissolved leaving copper behind. In the latter, it is assumed that initially both copper and zinc are dissolved, followed by redeposition of copper.

The earliest observation is that of Calvert and Johnson¹, who showed that an alloy of equal proportions of copper and zinc, immersed in concentrated hydrochloric acid, gave up in a few days the whole of zinc, leaving behind copper in spongy state. Tilden² considered the role of oxygen in the corrosion of brass and showed that no corrosion of brass took place if air were excluded.

Philip³ believed in the existence of minute zinc-copper couples functioning as small electric cells all over the surface of the brass. Due to such couples the zinc is dissolved, leaving the copper behind.

Colegate⁴ classified dezincification in two types: (a) plug type and (b) layer type, according as the dezincification penetrates perpendicularly or spreads horizontally on the specimen. The division is arbitrary and merely indicates whether corrosion is localized or general.

Bengough and Hudson⁵ consider that copper is not residual but is of 'redeposited' type. According to these authors, when brass is placed in chloride solution, the first attack affords a layer of copper oxide with a little zinc oxide, the zinc mainly going into solution as zinc chloride. The oxidised surface gradually changes into an almost insoluble cuprous chloride, which is ordinarily swept away by gravity or water currents, but which may adhere to the surface. If the insoluble chlorides adhere to the surface, cupric chloride is formed. Cupric chloride attacks zinc as well as copper, with formation of a soluble zinc chloride and deposition of a crystalline or powdery copper.

The transformation of brass to copper was once known as dezincification, but Bengough, Jones and Pirret⁵ were the first to demonstrate clearly the redeposited part of copper. They termed this "apparent dezincification" to distinguish it from chemical dezincification of leaching out of the baser zinc metal.

Abrams⁷ concluded that agitation favoured complete corrosion, whereas stagnation favoured dezincification. He further stated that maintenance of a film was necessary for dezincification. According to him dezincification may be obtained by artificial films, which would prevent removal of copper and cuprous salts.

The presence of a considerable amount of dissolved copper would also permit dezincification even in absence of a membrane. Bengough and May⁸ confirmed Abrams' findings and further made a classical observation that small amounts of arsenic in brass could prevent dezincification.

Stillwell and Turnipseed⁹ studied the corrosion of ϵ -brass and showed that powerful reagents like concentrated hydrochloric acid attacked both copper and zinc, copper being subsequently redeposited. On the other hand, weak reagents like dilute hydrochloric acid or acetic acid remove only the zinc atoms converting ϵ -brass first to γ -brass then to β -brass, and finally leaving residual copper. The weak reagents favour chemical dezincification, but strong reagents favour apparent dezincification.

Fink and Evans¹⁰ state that in the initial stage of attack, the corrosion may consist of selective solution of zinc producing copper-rich areas, which may then promote electrochemical action. Evans¹¹ states that the effective reactions in either case are the same.

According to him, thus the driving E.M. F. should be the same for both mechanisms, but in the first mechanism (residual copper theory) the resistance must soon become high since zinc ions have to thread their way through very fine pores in the copper. It is not easy to see how the first mechanism can persist after the first few atomic layers of brass have become dezincified. The first mechanism is important at the outset. The action usually starts at points abnormally rich in zinc, such as the grain boundaries where traces of β phase may be present even in 70/30 (α) brass¹². Zinc-rich places will be anodic and both copper and zinc will dissolve. When copper compounds have sufficiently accumulated, metallic copper may be redeposited and the second mechanism can then continue.

There is considerable evidence in support of both the theories. Thus, Milton and Larke¹³, Bassett¹⁴, Polushkin¹⁵, and Bialosky¹⁶ consider that copper is residual, whereas Bengough and May⁸, Hollomen and Wulff¹⁷, Abrams⁷, and Storey¹⁸ are of the opinion that it is redeposited.

One of the factors influencing dezincification is the oxygen concentration of the solution. Low degree of aeration favours dezincification, whereas high degree of aeration brings about complete corrosion. High chloride ion concentration is also effective in inducing dezincification. Coupling of brass to a more cathodic metal may induce dezincification, but contact with anodic metal may prevent dezincification. Increase in the zinc content

of the alloy increases its susceptibility to dezincification. A mixture of α - and β -alloys is more susceptible than α -alloys. Arsenic and tin are good inhibitors of dezincification as these prevent deposition of copper. A practical remedy for dezincification exists for the α -brasses but not yet for the two-phase brasses. Arsenic appears to pass preferentially into the α phase leaving the more susceptible β phase unprotected. On the other hand, the addition of 1% tin to the two-phase brass reduces the rate of dezincification considerably. It is possible that the addition of tin or arsenic to brass so modifies the deposition potential of copper that deposition of initially dissolved copper is stopped. Retardation in dezincification may also be due to the fact that tin has a high hydrogen overpotential and that arsenic raises the hydrogen overpotential at a cathode.

Corrosion of various brasses such as α -brass (80/20, 70/30, 60/40) and $\alpha + \beta$ -brass (59/41) has been studied by us in the presence of various acids and salts¹⁹. In an attempt to study the corrosion of brass we have tried to find out whether it is possible to distinguish clearly between the two types of dezincification and also to find out ways and means of reducing dezincification by modifying the medium. The dezincification is evident in the case of hydrochloric acid, phosphoric acid, and lactic acid. The action of these reagents alone may result in dezincification depending on the nature and concentration of the reagent and duration of the experiment. In some cases, such as malic, citric, and tartaric acids, there may initially be decuprification. This is due to complex formation between copper and anions of these acids.

The influence of H_2O_2 on corrosion by the acids afforded interesting results. In the case of α -brass, addition of H_2O_2 invariably results in reduction of dezincification to such an extent that there may even be cases of copper being preferentially dissolved. In presence of H_2O_2 , deposited copper is redissolved or prevented from being redeposited. The addition of H_2O_2 favours complex formation between copper and anions of these acids. According to Evans' stagnant condition favours dezincification, whereas aeration favours dissolution of the alloy as a whole. Addition of H_2O_2 may be beneficial in pickling of α -brass as it would reduce dezincification. The behaviour is quite different in the case of $\alpha + \beta$ brass. Addition of small amounts of H_2O_2 results in increase of dezincification. This is in accordance with the observation of Uhlig²⁰, that corrosion of zinc is accelerated in presence of oxygen. Even in $\alpha + \beta$ -brass, further addition of H_2O_2 leads, however, to a decrease in dezincification. In presence of small amounts of H_2O_2 , the attack on β phase is augmented; further addition of H_2O_2 , however, results in attack of both the phases. Thus small amounts of H_2O_2 clearly distinguishes electrochemical and chemical dezincification, former being reduced and the latter being increased.

The study of the influence of inhibitors on the corrosion of α - (60/40) and $\alpha + \beta$ - (59/41) brasses by NH_4Cl (1.0*N*—5 days) revealed the following results:

TABLE I

(Size of the specimen = 6 cm × 3 cm. Thickness = 28. s.w.g.)

Reagent.	α -Brass (60.7% Cu-39.1% Zn)		$\alpha + \beta$ -Brass (59/41).	
	Corrosion.	Ratio (Cu/Zn).	Corrosion.	Ratio (Cu/Zn).
Blank (1.0 <i>N</i> - NH_4Cl)	36.6 mg.	0.0139	41.7 mg.	0.0024
Agar (0.2%)	85% Reduction		87% Reduction	—
Dextrin (0.2%)	102% Increase	0.93	25% "	0.030
Acacia (0.2%)	175% "	0.98	47% "	0.023
Gelatin (0.2%)	252% "	0.80	12% Increase	0.80
Urea (0.2%)	295% "	1.48	3% "	0.0024

Agar reduces corrosion to nearly 1/6th the value in the case of both the brasses. Hence it may be employed as a general inhibitor. For α -brass gelatine, dextrine, acacia, or urea increases attack and reduces dezincification. In the case of $\alpha + \beta$ -brass, urea has practically no influence on the mode and extent of corrosion, whereas the attack is retarded in the case of acacia and dextrin. The action of these reagents may serve to distinguish between chemical and electrochemical dezincification. Urea is the best example. It increases corrosion when dezincification is of the electrochemical type, but is without any influence on the mode and extent of corrosion where dezincification is of the leaching type. Gelatine is the only inhibitor which reduces dezincification of $\alpha + \beta$ -brass.

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REFERENCES

1. Calvert and Johnson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1866, **19**, 436.
2. Tilden, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1886, **5**, 84.
3. Philip, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1915, **11**, 244.
4. Colegate, *Metal Ind.*, 1948, 483.
5. Bengough and Hudson, *Chem. Met. Eng.*, 1922, **15**, 305.
6. Bengough, Jones, and Pirret, *J. Inst. Met.*, 1920, **23**, 113.
7. Abrams, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1922, **42**, 39.
8. Bengough and May, *J. Inst. Met.*, 1924, **32**, 183.
9. Stillwell and Turnipseed, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1934, **26**, 740.
10. Fink and Evans, *Trans. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1939, **75**, 441.
11. Evans, "The Corrosion and Oxidation of Metals", Edward Arnold & Co., 1960, p. 475.
12. de Wrustumberger, *Rev. Met.*, 1921, **18**, 702.
13. Milton and Lark, *Proc. Inst. Civil Eng.*, 1903, **154**, 138.
14. Bassett, *Chem. Met. Eng.*, 1922, **27**, 340.
15. Polushkin and Shuldener, *Corrosion*, 1946, **2**, 1.
16. Bialosky, "Corrosion and Material Protection", 1947, **41**, 15.
17. Holloman and Wulff, *Met. Tech.*, 1942, 9.
18. Storey, *Met. Chem. Eng.*, 1917, **17**, 653.
19. Desai and Trivedi, *J. Gujarat Univ.*, Science Number, 1958, **41**; *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1958, **21**, 137; 1960, **23**, 1r;
Desai, Talati, and Trivedi, *Werks. u. Korrosion*, 1959, **10**, 26; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, **18B**, 214;
Indian J. Appl. Chem., 1959, **22**, 45.
20. Uhlig, "The Corrosion Hand Book", John Wiley & Sons, 1953, p. 333.